

D3.3 – Appliances components 3D design

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Contributors	
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1 Executive Summary

The SMARTFAN grant aims to develop and define “smart” material and product architectures, with integrated functionalities, that will interact with the environment and react to stimuli by employing self-sensing, actuating and advanced technologies.

ELICA project focuses on the development of an innovative conveyor/impeller for air treatment applications, based on computational fluid dynamics simulations able to characterize the geometry of the new device taking into account smart materials physical properties and external stimuli as an influence parameter. The purpose of the research is to achieve the optimized design of a new high efficiency blower exploiting smart materials innovative features.

In the present document, the definition of the design of an axial impeller for the SMARTFAN ELICA application will be reviewed. In particular, in the second chapter, the optimization flow is presented, with a focus on the role of the CFD simulation, which supported the optimization process.

2 Axial impeller design

The fan shall be appropriate both for cooker hoods and for any other application related to indoor air quality treatment. It consists of an axial fan where the polymer changes its geometry, in particular the one of the blade profile, in order to optimize the performance of the entire system. The new system will be able to work in many different conditions, in terms of airflow, pressure and temperature, always with a high efficiency level, increasing the fluid dynamic behaviour, which is mainly affected by the blade profile. These features request ELICA to design a new axial fan specifically intended for this use.

The axial fan will be modelled in order to work with the same high efficiency in both flow direction, because of the blade shape modification, which depends on the external stimuli related to the flow direction.

The new system will show sensitivity to the following physical signals:

- 1) SMARTFAN shall be able to react to temperature signals
- 2) SMARTFAN shall be able to react to air pressure signals.

The temperature monitoring might allow the change of the fan/impeller speed in order to increase the motor efficiency, which is closely related to the temperature. The pressure monitoring permits the detection of the correct working parameters.

To work properly the whole system shall be driven by a microcontroller and a proper FW to:

- Read data from sensing parts
- Elaborate data to proper algorithms
- Drive fans (according also to mechanical properties change).

Therefore, the final device will have innovative properties directly derived from the new characteristics of the smart materials of which is made of.

Figure 2.1: Axial fan.

In order to define the properties of a device able to show these smart features, an optimization process took place. This optimization process was supported by a CFD simulation. Through the CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamic) is possible to realize a computer aided simulation in order to evaluate of all fluid dynamic parameters that characterize a physical system (this will be explained widely in following paragraphs).

2.1 Goals of the optimization process

Goal of the optimization process was to define the geometric properties of the axial fan (blades number and their shape in particular), in order to obtain high values of the Fluid Dynamic Efficiency (FDE) and uniform pressure fields on the blades of the impeller.

At first, a “first try” axial impeller was designed and its fluid dynamic properties were calculated through a CFD simulation. The results of this analysis were utilized as reference point for the realization of successive axial impellers.

In order to obtain an increase of volumetric flow rate, the second axial impeller had less blades than the first one (7 instead of 9). The CFD analysis shows that the aim was obtained, but there was no increase of the FDE parameter and the pressure field was similar to the previous one (in terms of uniformity).

The increase of FDE was obtained modifying blades shape (in accordance to Euler’s Law). The FDE increase was evaluated through the CFD analysis.

Finally, the external diameter was reduced in order to make the axial impeller geometrically compatible with the both technologies that will utilize this component.

Following, a chart that recapitulates the geometric properties of the impellers.

Axial impellers characteristics					
	VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE 1	VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE 2	VIRTUAL PROTOTYPE 3	FINAL DESIGN	
D int	44	44	40	47	mm
D ext	135	135	135	114	mm
thickness	25	25	25	17	mm
blades nr	9	7	7	7	

Table 2.1: Axial impellers geometric properties.

2.2 CFD-aided optimization process

In this paragraph, the optimization process will be more widely explained and all CFD simulation results will be reported.

2.2.1 Virtual prototype 1

As already said, a “first try” impeller was designed and then analysed in order to define a base point for the optimization process. This impeller has been named “virtual prototype 1” and its geometric dimensions were reported in Table 2.1.

Figure 2.2: virtual prototype 1

The axial impeller performance was evaluated in term of pressure, volumetric flow rate and FDE. All these parameters were calculated through a CFD simulation.

A CFD simulation is composed of three parts:

- Realization of the geometry of the system. In this case, two different parts were defined, a static part and a rotating part. The impeller is included in the rotating part, while the static part comprehends a “quiet room”, which simulates the external room, and a pipe.

Figure 2.3: system geometry

- Generation of a 3D “mesh”. A mesh is a calculation grid that discretize the physical domain in order to allow the solution of the fluid-dynamic equations. The mesh shall respect some quality constraints in order to get a reliable solution.

In fact, the discretization of the physic domain shall allow the correct resolution of the fluid dynamic equations and the respect of mesh quality constraints represent a control on the accuracy of the results. Main quality constraints are:

- Orthogonal quality min > 0.01 ;
- Skewness max < 0.97
- Aspect ratio max < 1000

Since the system geometry was made of two parts, two different mesh were generated and then they were connected through interfaces.

Figure 2.4: interfaces

Following figures show the generated mesh.

Figure 2.5: static part mesh

Figure 2.6: rotating part mesh

- Last step concerns the definition of the physical condition of the system in term of fluid properties, boundary conditions, turbulence models, etc. Moreover, during this phase the calculation parameters are set.
The physical setup is a representation of the real system, meaning that the results of the simulation shall be as close as possible to the real application.

CALCULATION SETUP		
STATIC PART	Fluid	ideal air at 25°C
	Reference pressure	1 atm
	Inlet	0 Pa
	Outlet	variable mass flow
	Quiet room	free slip walls
	Real walls	no slip walls
	Turbulence model	Shear Stress Transport
ROTATING PART	Fluid	ideal air at 25°C
	Reference pressure	1 atm
	Angular speed	2400 rpm
	Real walls	no slip walls
	Turbulence model	Shear Stress Transport
INTERFACE	Models	General connection/ Frozen Rotor
CALCULATION	Analysis type	Steady state
	Iterations	3000
	RMS	10 ⁻⁷

Table 2.2: physical setup and calculation settings

Figure 2.7: setup

As output of the CFD calculation, two curves are reported:

- Pressure – Volumetric flow rate (figure 8)
- FDE – Volumetric flow rate (figure 9)

Figure 2.8: pressure – volumetric flow rate curves

Figure 2.9: FDE – volumetric flow rate curves

- Maximum pressure value: 40.3 Pa
- Maximum flow rate value: 140 m³/h
- Maximum FDE value: 5.3%

These curves are the base point for the optimization process.

Moreover, since the impeller shall be able to react to the air pressure, the pressure field on blades has been evaluated.

Figure 2.10: pressure field on blades

The “contour” on blades surface shows that the pressure field is not uniform.

2.2.2 Virtual prototype 2

Goal of this step of the optimization process was the evaluation of how an increase of volumetric flow rate affects the pressure field on the blades surface. It was decided to increase the volumetric flow rate by reducing the number of blades. In fact, a lower number of blade means an increase of passage surface for the airflow. For this reason, the second virtual prototype presents seven blades instead of nine.

This impeller has been named “virtual prototype 2” and its geometric dimensions were reported in Table 2.1.

Figure 2.11: virtual prototype 2

“Virtual prototype 2” performance was evaluated through another CFD simulation, which follows the same steps that were reported in previous paragraph:

- Concerning geometry, the new impeller was included in the rotating part, while the static part did not change

Figure 2.12: system geometry

- Static part mesh did not change, while rotating part mesh is shown below

Figure 2.13: rotating part mesh

- The physical setup and the calculation settings are the same as shown in table 2.2.

Performance curves (pressure – volumetric flow rate and FDE – volumetric flow rate curves) are reported below compared with virtual prototype 1 curves.

Figure 2.14: pressure – volumetric flow rate curves

Figure 2.15: FDE – volumetric flow rate curves

- Maximum pressure value: 37 Pa
- Maximum flow rate value: 180 m³/h
- Maximum FDE value: 5.1%

The aim of this step of the optimization process was reached. In fact, maximum volumetric flow rate value increased from 140 to 180 m³/h. It is worth noting that the other parameters are not much different from previous case.

Finally, the pressure field on blades is reported.

Figure 2.16: pressure field on blades

Figure 6 shows that the uniformity of pressure field on the blades has not been obtained.

2.2.3 Virtual prototype 3

The goal of this step is to obtain an increase of the maximum FDE value. The shape of the blades was determined using the Euler's law for axial impeller:

$$work = \frac{c_1^2 - c_2^2}{2} + \frac{w_2^2 - w_1^2}{2} \left[\frac{J}{kg} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.17: velocity triangles

“c” is the airflow velocity in an absolute reference system while “w” is the airflow velocity in a relative reference system that is integral with the blade. “c₁” and “w₁” refer to the fan inlet while “c₂” and “w₂” refer to the fan outlet. “u” is the tangential velocity of the blade ($u = \text{radius} \cdot \text{angular velocity}$) and for an axial impeller it does not change from inlet to outlet.

Through a variation of the shape of the blades, a more uniform pressure field on blades was expected.

The resulting axial impeller has been named “virtual prototype 3” and its geometric dimensions were reported in Table 2.1

Figure 2.18: virtual prototype 3

The steps of the CFD analysis are reported below (similarly to the previous paragraph):

- The new impeller was included in the rotating part

Figure 2.19: system geometry

- Static part mesh did not change, while rotating part mesh is shown below

Figure 2.20: rotating part mesh

- The physical setup and the calculation settings are the same as shown in table 2.2.

Performance curves (pressure – volumetric flow rate and FDE – volumetric flow rate curves) are reported below compared with virtual prototype 1 and virtual prototype 2 curves.

Figure 2.21: pressure – volumetric flow rate curves

Figure 2.22: FDE – volumetric flow rate curves

- Maximum pressure value: 42 Pa
- Maximum flow rate value: 220 m³/h
- Maximum FDE value: 11.3%

The aim of this step of the optimization process was reached. In fact, maximum FDE value increased from 5.1 to 11.3 %. The maximum volumetric flow rate value increase as well.

Finally, the pressure field on blades is reported.

Figure 2.23: pressure field on blades

In this case, pressure field on blades started to be more uniform that before, even if the maximum pressure value does not significantly change.

2.2.4 Final design

Previous optimization steps allowed the definition of the number of blades and their shape, in order to guarantee a high value of fluid dynamic efficiency and an uniform pressure field on blades.

In order to adapt the impeller geometry to both proposed applications, another optimization step was necessary. In fact, if the impeller could be integrated both in an array of axial impellers contained inside a hood and in the Elica SNAP, a significant optimization of the industrial process would be obtained.

Figure 2.24: hood that contains an Array of eight fans (left) and Elica SNAP (right)

For this reason, the final design presents a reduction of the external diameter and the thickness of the axial fan, as shown in Table 2.1. Moreover, the shape of the blades was improved.

Figure 2.25: final design of the axial fan

One last CFD analysis was made in order to evaluate the final design performance.

- The new impeller was included in the rotating part

Figure 2.26: system geometry

- Static part mesh did not change, while rotating part mesh is shown below

Figure 2.27: rotating part mesh

- The physical setup did not change, while the number of iteration was increased from 3000 to 3500

Performance curves (pressure – volumetric flow rate and FDE – volumetric flow rate curves) are reported below compared with previous virtual prototypes curves.

Figure 2.28: pressure – volumetric flow rate curves

Figure 2.29: FDE – volumetric flow rate curves

- Maximum pressure value: 20 Pa
- Maximum flow rate value: 150 m³/h
- Maximum FDE value: 14.3%

Even if the maximum pressure value and the maximum flow rate value are lower than before, the maximum FDE increased.

It is worth noting that even if maximum pressure value of the final configuration results much lower than before, this final axial impeller would fit both proposed technologies. The decrease of maximum pressure would be balanced by the flexibility allowed by a single design of the impeller.

Moreover, the pressure field on blades results to be more uniform than previous virtual prototypes.

Figure 2.30: pressure field on blades

3 Conclusions after the optimization process

Even if the final axial impeller does not show the maximum values of outlet pressure and volumetric flow rate, the two main aims of the optimization process were reached:

- High Fluid Dynamic Efficiency
- Uniform pressure field on blades
- Geometric dimensions suitable for both proposed applications

The results of the optimization process are recapitulated in the following table.

D ext [mm]	blades nr	P max [Pa]	Q max [m ³ /h]	FDE BEP [%]
135				
Virtual prototype 1	9	40	140	5,3
Virtual prototype 2	7	39	180	5,1
Virtual prototype 3	7	42	220	11,3
114				
final design	7	20	150	14,3

Table 3.1: optimization process recap

Following Table recapitulates all mesh features and shows that all quality constraints were respected.

	mesh features	virtual prototype 1	virtual prototype 2	virtual prototype 3	final design
Static mesh	number of elements	327709	330334	341566	300310
	orthogonal quality min	0,10277	0,10054	0,10124	0,1005
	skewness max	0,89723	0,89946	0,89876	0,8995
	aspect ratio max	417,64	417,59	417,41	416,07
Rotating mesh	number of elements	679003	563040	550409	901786
	orthogonal quality min	0,11509	3,1456*10 ⁻²	0,16893	0,11705
	skewness max	0,88491	0,96854	0,83107	0,88295
	aspect ratio max	33,309	101,23	31,134	32,801

Table 3.2: mesh features recap

5 Deviations from DoA

There are no deviations to be reported. The technical work has been developed according to the plan and goals defined in the DoA.

6 The next six months

In the next six three months described procedures will be applied to standard reference samples and to an existing fan moulded with new material developed by other partners. In detail next steps are:

- manufacturing of standard square samples using materials developed from other partners
- Testing of the samples to verify the thermal and flammability features
- Manufacturing of an existing impeller using materials developed from other partners
- Test of the impeller to verify the thermal and flammability features
- Test of the impeller in a standard application to verify materials vs life test

These advances will be reported. within D2.9

7 Conclusion

In the present report the material specifications for domestic air treatment application -smart-fan/ impeller have been delivered as well as the testing procedure has been reviewed. No update to the document is currently expected unless there will be international regulations modification during the project development. In this case, or other critical issues, document shall be updated.

8 References

- [1] F.P. Bleier, “Fan Handbook: selection, application, and design”, McGraw Hill
- [2] Della Volpe R., “Macchine”, Liguori Editore
- [3] Ansys, “ANSYS CFX Tutorial”

9 Appendix

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